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ANALYZING THE GREEN HRM PRACTICES AND THEIR IMPACTS ON THE CORPORATE IMAGE OF SMES

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The green HRM practices create positive impacts on the brand image of SMEs. The increasing market size of this segment reflects that most of SMEs take initiative to adopt green HRM. On the other hand, this practices decrease the employee retention that is one of major issue.

Aim: The research aim is to analysis the impacts of green HRM practices on corporate image for different SMEs.

Literature review: Understand the concept of green HRM practice that will increase the brand reputation by promoting sustainable development practices. The higher cost for this practice brings barriers.

Methodology: Primary data methods will uses that include primary data collection and the primary quantitative data analysis method.

Findings: The impact of green HRM analyzed that help to increase the brand reputation as well as protect environment by using natural resources.

Discussion: Working culture and employee motivation help to adopt HRM practices that brings more productivity. By practices sustainable development, SMEs increase their image in the competitive market that brings effective competitive advantages. Maintaining culture helps to increase the adoption rate of green HRM.

Conclusion: The higher rate of employee retention as well as employee motivation help to increase the productivity that will meet customer satisfactions as a result, SMEs increases their reputation.

Keywords: SMEs, Green HRM, Carbon footprints, Employee retention, Corporate Image

Introduction: In this 21st century, most SMEs organization shows their tendency to practice green HRM. Green HRM practices are one of the major key aspects that help SMEs to achieve their sustainable development. Green HRM practices refer to the HRM practices that are mainly related uses of different HRM policies that help support the use of natural resources and preserve the environment (Ali et al. 2020). By implementing green practices, HRM can increase the rate of achievement of sustainable goals. Green practice increases the brand reputation of SMEs by reducing the overall cost as well as protecting the environment by uses of different natural resources for organizational activities (Wen et al. 2022).

FIGURE 1: MARKET SIZE OF HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT (HRM)

(Source: grandviewresearch.com, 2020)

Figure 1 represents the enhancement of market size for HRM. As per the above graphical image, in the financial year 2020, the total market size of the HRM is 4.8 billion US dollars that increased its adoption of green practicing aspects. In the financial year 2021, the total market increased by 8 percent and the value of this market is 5.2 billion US dollars (grandviewresearch.com, 2020).

This research study aims to analyze the impacts of green HRM practices on the organizational image of different SMEs.

The objectives of this research study are

- To understand the concept of Green HRM practices in the SMEs
- To evaluate the impacts of practicing green HRM on brand image for different SMEs
- To identify different challenges faced due to the adoption of green HRM by SMEs
- To recommend some effective strategies to increase the practices of green HRM

The research questions are

RQ 1: What is the concept of green HRM practices for SMEs?

RQ 2: What are the ways to green HRM practices create impacts on the corporate image of different SMEs?

RQ 3: What are the major challenges faced by SMEs due to the adoption of green HRM?

RQ 4: What are the effective strategies that help SMEs to adopt HRM practices?

The researcher of this research study identifies the main issue that is analyzing green HRM practices, which create impacts on the SME's corporate image. Due to adoption of the green HRM practices, organizations faced a higher rate of employee turnover (Amjad et al. 2021).

Due to failing to adopt cultural changes in the organization's activities, Most of the SMEs faced higher rates of employee turnover that created negative impacts on corporate image.

LITERATURE REVIEW

CONCEPT OF GREEN HRM PRACTICES

Figure 2: Concept of Green HRM

(Source: Malik et al. 2021)

Figure 2 provides information about the Green HRM. As per the study by Li et al. (2023), Green HRM refers to some effective organization; policies r practices that will help an organization to increase sustainable business practices. Here, this aspect will also increase employment engagement as a result; the employee gets more satisfaction that creates positive impacts on the corporate image of the different SMEs. On the other hand, Malik et al. (2021) argued that Green HRM not only promotes

sustainable business practices, it also increases the efficiency of the SMEs that bring future growth. Through this HRM practice, an organization can reduce the carbon footprints that would to protect the environment positively.

DIFFERENT WAYS TO CREATE IMPACTS ON THE CORPORATE IMAGE BY PRACTICING GREEN HRM

Figure 3: HRM practices help to achieve an effective organizational image
(Source: Labella-Fernández & Martínez-del-Río, 2019)

Figure 3 is related to the increase in brand image through green HRM practices. As per the review of Mousa & Othman (2020), green HRM practices provide effective green training and development to the employees that will help employees in the career development segment. Through career advancement, SMEs can increase the satisfaction level of employees which brings a positive corporate reputation. On the other hand, Labella-Fernández & Martínez-del-Río (2019) argued that employees get green appraisals that will enhance employee motivation. By increasing employee motivation, SMEs are increased their productivity which helps to meet customer demand, as a result, increase the corporate image have seen.

CHALLENGES FACED BY SMES DUE TO THE ADOPTION OF GREEN HRM

Figure 4: Challenges faced by SMEs during adaptation of Green HRM
(Source: Wen et al. 2022)

Figure 4 provides information on the challenges faced by SMEs by adopting green HRM. As per the investigation Wen et al. (2022), due to the adoption of green HRM, an increase in the cost for SMEs has been seen. Here, the organization faced the higher costs of organizational activities that decreased profitability. On the other hand, Islam et al. (2021) stated that due to green HRM practices, the

employee turnover rate increased. Employees in different SMEs did not inspire by the green practices that affected the employment aspects. In terms of challenges faced by SMEs that are SMEs did not get organization support which includes support for employees as well as regulatory bodies and other departments that create negative impacts on the organization's reputation.

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES HELP TO INCREASE THE ADAPTATION OF GREEN HRM

Figure 5: Recommendations to increase the adaptation of green HRM

(Source: Al Doghan et al.2022)

In terms of increasing the adoption of green HRM practices in different SMEs, organizations should take some effective strategies. As per the study by Al Doghan et al. (2022), SMEs should improve the culture of the workplace which will help to adopt new practices and the recommendations shown in Figure 5. Through green practices, HRM can increase organizational productivity through increase the motivation level among employees. On the other hand, SMEs should provide training about the corporate culture that helps to adopt green HRM. The organization should include a sustainable achievement program that brings interest to adopting green HRM practices in organizational activities (Amjad et al. 2021).

Methodology: The researcher of this research study uses primary research methodology to get an unbiased outcome from the research work. To collect data, the researcher uses the primary data collection process to get more accurate data or information. As per the study by Li, Higgins & Deeks (2019), primary data collection is a data collection process that includes collecting data from different non existing sources. In terms of non-existing sources, the process includes online surveys as well as interviews etc. The researcher of this research study uses an online survey to collect data on the impact of green HRM practices on the corporate image of different SMEs. Here, the researcher asked 13 different questions that include 3 demographic questions and other 10 questions research work related. For the online survey, the researcher uses Google-Form and there are a total of 90 employees from different SMEs took participated in this online survey.

Data analysis: The researcher of this research study uses a primary quantitative data analysis method that provided statistical analysis. In this analysis segment, the researcher uses IBM SPSS statistical tool that provides descriptive as well as linear regression and Pearson correlation analysis among different dependent and independent variables (Fang & Liu, 2021). Through the help of statistical analysis, the researcher gets an unbiased result which helps in the data interpretation segment.

FINDINGS

DEMOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

AGE

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	27	30.0	30.0	30.0
	2	18	20.0	20.0	50.0
	3	18	20.0	20.0	70.0
	4	27	30.0	30.0	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 6: Age-frequency of respondents

As per the above graphical image, 30 percent of respondents have an aged between 25 years to 30 years. On the other hand, 41-50 years respondents are 30 percent. The other two groups have ages between 31-35 and 36-40 years.

GENDER

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	18	20.0	20.0	20.0
	2	54	60.0	60.0	80.0
	3	18	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 7: Gender of respondents

As per the above graphical image, there is 60 percent of respondents are female categories whereas males and others have 20 percent respondents respectively. Through the help of the online survey, respondents provide their valuable information about the research work.

EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION

Educational_qualification					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	9	10.0	10.0	10.0
	2	36	40.0	40.0	50.0
	3	45	50.0	50.0	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 8: Educational qualification of participants

As per the above image, 10 percent of respondents have higher secondary qualifications whereas 50 percent of people have postgraduate degrees. On the other hand, 40 percent of respondents who completed their graduation provided valuable feedback on the research work.

LINEAR REGRESSION ANALYSIS

IV1

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.816 ^a	.666	.662	1.61278	.666	175.316	1	88	.000	2.393

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV1
b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	456.007	1	456.007	175.316	.000 ^b
	Residual	228.893	88	2.601		
	Total	684.900	89			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), IV1

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.649	.350		1.855	.067
	IV1	.664	.050	.816	13.241	.000

a. Dependent Variable: DV

Table 1: Linear regression analysis for IV1

As per the above table, the R square value is .666 which is greater than 0.05 as a result, this value signified this independent variable 1. On the other hand, the F value for this IV is 175.316 that signified this independent variable. In terms of the coefficient test, the t value is 13.241, which is greater than 0.5 and that signified a 0.00 level. In this analysis, the Durbin Watson value is 2.393 that is positive and offers unbiased result.

IV2

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.773 ^a	.598	.594	1.76844	.598	131.000	1	88	.000	2.401

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV2
b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	409.689	1	409.689	131.000	.000 ^b
	Residual	275.211	88	3.127		
	Total	684.900	89			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), IV2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.151	.362		3.182	.002
	IV2	.612	.053	.773	11.446	.000

a. Dependent Variable: DV

Figure 2: Linear regression analysis for IV2

As per the above regression analysis table, in the model summary test, the R square value is 0.598 that signifies the independent variable 2 related to the Green HRM is an important key aspect for the SMEs. Here F value is 131.000 and the mean square value is 409.689 which signified this variable that gets by the researcher by doing the ANOVA test. In terms of the coefficient test, the researcher get a t value that is 11.446 which is greater than 0.5 and the standardized coefficient value of this variable is 0.773 and this positive value provides an effective outcome that helps in the data interpretation segment. In the model summary test, Durbin Watson value is 2.401.

IV3

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.710 ^a	.504	.498	1.96545	.504	89.298	1	88	.000	2.728

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV3
b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	344.956	1	344.956	89.298	.000 ^b
	Residual	339.944	88	3.863		
	Total	684.900	89			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), IV3

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.499	.397		3.776	.000
	IV3	.821	.087	.710	9.450	.000

a. Dependent Variable: DV

Figure 3: Linear regression analysis for IV3

In terms of IV 3, the researcher did a linear regression analysis. Here the R square value is .504 and this positive value signified this variable effectively. In this analysis method, the F value is 89.298 and the mean square value is 3.863 positive. In this context, the Durbin Watson value is 2.728 for this independent variable. On the other hand, the t value for this variable is 9.450 that signified at the 0.000 level.

Correlations					
		DV	IV1	IV2	IV3
DV	Pearson Correlation	1	.816**	.773**	.710**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	90	90	90	90
IV1	Pearson Correlation	.816**	1	.983**	.954**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	90	90	90	90
IV2	Pearson Correlation	.773**	.983**	1	.947**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	90	90	90	90
IV3	Pearson Correlation	.710**	.954**	.947**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	90	90	90	90

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 4: “Pearson Bivariate Correlation”

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

As per the above analysis, the Pearson correlation test has been seen. Here the dependent variable makes correlations with I1 at the 0.01 level. On the other hand, IV1 also makes a relationship with the other two IV and DV at 0.001 level which two-tailed. The IV3 makes relationships with IV1 as well as IV2 and DV at 0.01 levels.

DISCUSSION

In organizational activities, green HRM practice brings revolutionary changes. Through the help of green HRM, SMEs can motivate their employees to increase their interest level toward sustainable practices (Ercantan & Eyupoglu, 2022). On the other hand, it is an important key aspect for an organization that helps to reduce the cost of business studies. In terms of enhancement of brand reputation, green HRM practices help to protect the environment that increases the attraction for environmentally conscious people in the UK. As a result, increasing the business activities of those SMEs that practice Green HRM as a result, positive impacts on the corporate image have been seen. Through the help of green HRM, HR offers different types of training and career development seasons to the employees and this training activity will help them to get more knowledge (Mwita, 2020). By getting career development options, the employee gets more satisfaction that brings a higher rate of employee retention that creates impacts on corporate image.

In organizational activities, Green HRM encourages employees to achieve different sustainable goals of their organization. Here, these encouraging aspect brings lower amount of carbon footprints as a result, increasing brand image for SMEs has been seen that help in future growth. On the other hand, when Green HRM practices enhanced the organization's productivity, it will help to meet the customer's expectations that create positive impacts on the organizational image (Jam & Jamal, 2020).

CONCLUSION

In the end, it can be concluded that in this 21st century, SMEs show a tendency to adopt green HRM practices that create positive as well as negative impacts on the corporate image. With the increasing market size of HRM in the world, HRM plays a vital role in business activities. On the other hand, green HRM offers effective strategies to SMEs to reduce their operating cost that brings a higher rate of profitability. In terms of challenges, SMEs faced higher cost-related issue that mitigate through effective strategies.

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